

THE UZBEK MODEL OF SOCIAL AND CULTURAL DEVELOPMENT OF RURAL AREAS

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Abstract. This article analyzes some actual scientific and practical issues of economic and socio-cultural development of rural areas of Uzbekistan.

Keywords. territory, socio-cultural, economic development, agriculture, national model, development, urban, rural ethnoculture, lifestyle.

About half of the population of Uzbekistan, according to July 2022 data, 49.1 percent (17.9 million people) live in rural areas. This requires the study of socio-cultural development of rural areas as a separate topic. In addition, the rural way of life, culture, social thought is different from that of an urbanized city. During the years of independence, fundamental reforms were carried out in the field of modernization of the agro-complex, changing the image of the village in accordance with artistic and aesthetic requirements, expanding and mobilizing the relations between the city and the countryside. "Decision on" initiated the study of existing problems and their necessary solution in the form of a "road map". "Second sectors" were established, and they were directed to visit households in the regions, to

identify families in need of help, to prevent crimes and to improve the legal culture of the population. For example, in the territory of the "second sector" of the Kasbi district of the Kashkadarya region, there are 22 general education schools, 3 vocational colleges, 6 preschool educational institutions, 4 rural medical centers and family polyclinics, 3 emergency medical services, 3 shrines. , 102 shops, 2 farmers' markets, 6 pharmacies, 253 farms, 1 cultural and recreation center, 1 health center are registered. The economic and cultural life of these objects was analyzed, loans were allocated to families in need of financial assistance, youth and women employed, and water and gas supply problems were solved(1).

In the socio-cultural development of the regions, it is appropriate to remember first of all the state program "Obod Mahalla" and "Obod Kyshlo". This program, in our opinion, can be called a national, Uzbek model of socio-cultural development of regions, including rural areas. Over the next three years, within the framework of the program, more than 1,500 neighborhoods and rural areas were transformed into engineering-communication networks and socio-cultural spheres. More than nine thousand branches and facilities providing socio-cultural services to the population were launched (2).

The Action Strategy (2017-2022) and the Development Strategy (2022-2026) initiated by the President of our Republic Sh.M. Mirziyoyev, aimed at the modernization of our country, encouraged to further accelerate the changes in the "Prosperous Neighborhood" and "Prosperous Village" programs and raise them to a new level. The work carried out under the program was critically analyzed in the Resolution "On Measures for the Implementation of the "Prosperous Village" and "Prosperous Mahalla" Programs in 2022-2026 (March 18, 2022). It was found that there are serious social problems in 1,071 villages and neighborhoods, 179 neighborhoods and rural areas are built of straw or raw bricks, there are general education schools, and even in many remote villages and auls there are no cultural centers.

In 5,568 neighborhoods and rural areas, 29,000 kilometers of dirt roads are not paved, 1,540 are not provided with centralized drinking water, 49 have no public transport, and 781 have no garbage collection services (3). According to our own

calculations, about 80 percent of existing cultural and educational institutions in rural areas are either housed in adapted buildings or in need of major reconstruction. During the period of autocracy, rural libraries, together with their territories, were sold to entrepreneurs. Many such examples can be cited. How to ensure socio-cultural development of rural areas in this reality? the question arises. In our opinion, this problem should be solved by looking at the following routing system. First, the social and cultural sphere is a component of the national economy. Therefore, the development of the national economy in rural areas, primarily agriculture, is a guarantee of the improvement of the socio-cultural sphere as well. The Uzbek agricultural complex is a complex production complex with its infrastructure, production networks, logistics and external relations.

Considering that Uzbekistan is an agrarian country, we understand the position of agriculture in it. Agriculture affects the socio-cultural development of the village as a leading factor and sector. The second is to fundamentally update the appearance of rural areas, road-transport infrastructure, engineering and communication sectors.

This direction envisages the modernization of rural life, meeting the needs of the population for transport and communication services. It is difficult to imagine socio-cultural development without them. The government of our republic allocated 338 million US dollars for the period 2021-2025 for the implementation of the project "Sustainable development of rural areas" with the participation of the Islamic Development Bank and the OPEC International Development Fund.

200 million of it is the share of the Islamic Development Bank, 75 million of OPEC, 3.05 million of the United Nations Development Program and 59.95 million of Uzbekistan (4). This fund allocated for five years will serve to intensify the artistic and aesthetic appearance of Uzbek villages, centers of cultural and household services in residential areas, and relations between the village and the city. The agricultural complex and the settlements of the villagers are close to each other, and from the point of view of distance, it is not possible to go to work with two or three vehicles like in the city. This closeness encourages them to look at them as one object, their goals as one complex. True, the agrocomplex mainly consists of

production, labor process, processing of agricultural products and their delivery to cities.

Nevertheless, there is a permanent connection between the agricultural complex and the settlements of the villagers. Such settlements are the main source of productive forces for the agricultural complex. That is why the agricultural complex cannot be indifferent to the way of life of the rural population, the formation of rural youth, and the establishment of education. The third is that there is no "Chinese wall" between the neighborhood and the rural area, so it is necessary to understand that the status and opportunities of the neighborhood institution, which is the core of Uzbek ethnoculture, should be understood as also applicable to the rural areas. According to official data, construction and repair works of 436 schools, 208 pre-school education and 176 medical institutions have been completed within the framework of "Obad Mahalla" and "Obad Mahalla" program in our Republic until 2022. As a result, the number of prosperous and beautiful corners, charming houses, model houses and streets has increased in every region of our country. Our people's confidence in life has increased, and their aspiration to live and the future has become stronger. In a word, where there is prosperity, there is blessing, development, peace and abundance"(5).

Note that cultural institutions are not mentioned in the above speech. This situation is observed even in official decisions. That is why in the system of funds allocated from the state budget, the sphere of culture takes the last place. The mahallabay system and local entrepreneurship have a large contribution to the socio-cultural development of the regions.

Entrepreneurs, tenants, and neighborhood workers whose family life, lifestyle, and main activities are related to local areas can become the main force and factor that ensures the development of the area. In order to solve these problems, from December 2021, the position of the district (city) mayor's assistant was established, dealing with the issues of entrepreneurship development, employment provision and poverty reduction in neighborhoods and rural areas.

At the meeting of the video selector delivered by the President on April 19, 2022, it was said that unemployment is over 20% in 450 neighborhoods, that 140,000

people will be employed if livestock and poultry farming are supported in households, and that it is necessary to establish micro-industrial centers in neighborhoods (500 billion soums will be allocated from the state budget for this purpose).

It was noted that the first 1 month's salary of householders working in remote villages and village areas will be provided from the state budget. In our country, more than 2,000 neighborhoods are specialized in providing socio-economic and cultural services. In the future, the number of such specialized neighborhoods and regions will be increased, entrepreneurs operating in them, self-employed citizens will be supported. They are mainly engaged in services necessary for the population - household, crafts, gardening, poultry, fishing, beekeeping. The mahallabay system, unique to the Uzbek people, contributes greatly to the development of folk art, especially crafts. At the meeting, it was discussed the need to establish retail trade and cultural service centers in mahallas with a population of over 20,000. These centers are exempted from land and property taxes for a period of 5 years. (6). The increase of retail-trade and cultural-educational service centers will ensure socio-cultural development of the regions. Small and medium entrepreneurship plays an important role in socio-cultural development of regions. In the next three years, more than 400 Resolutions and Decrees of the President and the Cabinet of Ministers aimed at supporting entrepreneurship were announced. The year 2024 is designated as the Year of Youth and Entrepreneurship Support, and it is aimed at attracting young people in the regions to the economic and socio-cultural life, making wide use of their initiative and activity.

The Resolution of the President of April 20, 2022 "On measures to further expand the mechanisms of financing business projects in the regions" states that loans in the amount of Z00 million US dollars will be allocated to business entities for 7 years with a 3-year concession. At least 70 percent of the credit line funds will be allocated to entrepreneurs operating in areas other than the city of Nukus, administrative centers of the regions and cities under the jurisdiction of the region, that is, in rural areas (7). These credit funds are the largest, hitherto rare, means of financial support for entrepreneurs operating in the regions. In it, we see that serious, great attention is paid to the socio-cultural and economic development of the regions

of Karakalpakstan. The policy of our country aimed at reducing the complications of island Fiji is fully expressed in the national model of economic and socio-cultural development of the regions.

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